

Studies on the Interaction of Congo Red and Dodecyl Pyridinium Chloride

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The reaction between congo red and dodecyl pyridinium chloride has been investigated by conductometry and spectrophotometry. The conductometric studies show that the c.m.c. of the surfactant is lowered in presence of the dye. The addition of surfactant brings about a shift in the dye maxima. The results have been interpreted in terms of surfactant dye interaction and mixed micelle interaction.

The interaction of surface active agents with substances like proteins¹⁻⁴, polymers^{5,6}, nucleic acid⁷, hydrophobic sols^{8,9} and dyes¹⁰⁻¹⁴ has been studied by a number of workers to know physico-chemical behaviour of the surfactants. For quite some time we have been engaged with studies on surfactant dye interaction and have reported in a recent communication¹⁵ the quantitative studies on the binding of basic dyes to anionic surfactants and of acid dyes to cationic surfactants. The present communication reports the results of conductometric and colorimetric studies on the interaction of congo red and dodecylpyridinium chloride (DPC) in aqueous solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Congo red was a B.D.H. product and recrystallized from 50% alcohol. The cationic surfactant, viz., DPC was a Ruka (Switzerland) product.

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A Bausch and Lomb, 'spectronic 20' was used for light absorption measurements. The conductivity measurements were made with Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge, type CLOI/O1A.

Solutions were made in conductivity water throughout. Aqueous solutions containing different amounts of DPC and the dye were prepared in a number of pyrex boiling tubes, keeping the total volume constant. The tubes were allowed to stand for about 24 hours until all the precipitate had settled down. Both absorption and conductivity measurements were carried out by withdrawing the supernatant liquid, taking care to keep sediment undisturbed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Conductometric studies : The variation of specific conductance with surfactant concentration for aqueous solution of DPC, and DPC-congo red mixtures is given in Fig. 1. From the break in curve A, it is found that critical micelle concentration (c.m.c.) of pure DPC is $2.4 \times 10^{-2} M$. However, in presence of dye ($2 \times 10^{-5} M$) the break is shifted to lower

Fig. 1. Conductance of aqueous solution of DPC (curve A) and of DPC-congo red ($2 \times 10^{-5} M$) mixtures (curve B).

concentrations (Fig. 1, Curve B) and the micelle start forming at concentration of $1.4 \times 10^{-2} M$. The fact that c.m.c. in presence of dye is lowered from $2.4 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $1.4 \times 10^{-2} M$ indicates that dye takes part in micelle formation together with surfactant molecules. The participation of the dye in micelle formation is obviously through mixed micelle formation in which one or more dye molecules are associated with the surfactant micelle.

Colorimetric studies : Fig. 2 gives the absorbance of congo red-DPC mixtures at the absorption maximum of pure dye and the Table I gives the shift in absorption maximum of the dye as function of DPC concentration.

TABLE I

Effect of DPC on the absorption maximum of congo red ($2 \times 10^{-5} M$)

DPC concn. ($\times 10^{-5} M$)	0	1	2	3	1500	2000	3000	4000	5000	7000
Absorption maximum in $m\mu$	490	490	490	490	460	465	470	475	475	475

Fig. 2. Absorbance of DPC and congo red ($2 \times 10^{-5} M$) mixtures.

There can be several causes for spectral shift in the dye maximum on the addition of DPC. These are changes in pH of the dye solution, disturbance in the monomer-polymer equilibria of the dye, and the interaction between the dye and surfactant molecules. The possibility of the spectral shift due to the change in pH of dye solution is ruled out because the change in pH on the addition of DPC is almost negligible. Moreover, the dye has got the same absorption spectra, over a wide pH range viz., pH 5 to 9. The pH of all the solutions under discussion was maintained between 6.0 to 6.6.

The other possibility, viz., spectral shift due to the disturbance in monomer polymer equilibria is also ruled out since all the measurements were carried in the concentration range in which dye remains in the monomeric form. To confirm that the dye is only in monomeric form, absorbance of the dye solution at different concentrations was measured and it was found that for the concentration range employed in our investigations, the Beer's law was obeyed proving thereby that the dye is present only in monomeric form. It is, therefore, obvious that the change in absorption spectra is due to surfactant-dye interaction.

The congo red in aqueous solution is red in colour and exists in the following anionic form.

The above form has an absorption maximum at $490 m\mu$, when DPC is added to the dye, interaction takes place and the product precipitates out. It is seen from Fig. 2, that when the molar ratio of congo red to DPC is 1 : 2, the whole of the dye ($2 \times 10^{-5} M$) has interacted and the reaction product is precipitated out. The reaction may be assumed to be taking place due to coulombic attraction, the two surfactant cations combining with two SO_3^- sites on the dye anion. The absorption maximum of the dye also remains unchanged as the surfactant concentration is increased from 0 to $4 \times 10^{-5} M$, because the interaction product gets settled and the absorbance is only due to pure dye solution, no doubt, of lower concentration.

As the concentration of DPC is further increased, no change is observed (absorbance of the supernatant solution remains zero) until the concentration of DPC becomes $15 \times 10^{-3} M$. At this concentration the precipitated interaction product is solubilized and the solution has orange colour with an absorption maximum at $460 m\mu$. Since the interaction product is polar in nature and insoluble both in water and nonpolar solvents, it can be solubilized only through the mechanism of mixed micelle formation. Further we know from conductivity data that mixed micelle start forming at DPC concentration of $1.4 \times 10^{-2} M$.

As the concentration of DPC is further increased from $15 \times 10^{-3} M$, it is observed that absorbance of the solution increases and also the absorption maximum changes to higher wave-lengths. This change is due to the redistribution of dye molecules among the surfactant micelles. Initially (at DPC concentration of $15 \times 10^{-3} M$), the whole of the dye was distributed among the few surfactant micelles available and so the mixed micelles were rich in dye molecules and contained more than one dye molecule. As a result of the presence of a number of dye molecules in one micelle, the dye-dye interaction was possible and definitely affecting the absorption spectra of the solution. Now as we increase the DPC concentration, more surfactant micelles are available and, therefore, the dye molecules get redistributed among all the micelles. This causes a decrease in number of molecules per micelle and hence a change in absorbance due to the decrease in dye-dye interaction. A stage is reached when as result of redistribution of dye molecules and increase in number of micelles, only one dye molecule is present in one micelle and, therefore, further increase in DPC concentration will not affect the absorption spectra. It is evident from Table 1 and Fig. 2 that in the concentration range $15 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $40 \times 10^{-3} M$, the redistribution of dye takes place, causing a change in absorption maximum from 460 to $475 m\mu$. At $40 \times 10^{-3} M$, the redistribution of dye molecules is complete and, therefore, above this concentration no change in absorption maximum is noted.

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